

Fuel cell power module for electric forklift with integrated metal hydride hydrogen storage system

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Fuel cell powered forklifts have several advantages over the battery powered ones. They possess higher productivity by eliminating time consuming battery swap and can be refueled in 5-10 minutes. Fuel cell powered forklifts maintain constant power throughout entire shift as there is no voltage drop as compared to battery powered ones. They have higher initial cost but lower total logistic costs.

So far, almost all demonstrated FC powered utility vehicles used compressed H₂ stored in gas cylinders at pressures up to 350 bar. As a result, FC powered modules are too light, and additional balast is required for proper vehicle counterbalancing. Use of metal hydrides (MH) for the on-board hydrogen storage is promising alternative to solve this problem [1].

In 2012-2015, HySA Systems integrated a metal hydride H₂ storage extension tank in a commercial GenDrive 1600-80CEA fuel cell power module (Plug Power Inc.) which was installed in a 3 tonne STILL electric forklift [2]. This prototype is in operation at Impala Platinum refineries in Springs, South Africa, since September 2015, and the malfunctions identified were mainly related to Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC) battery.

In this work, we present a prototype fuel cell power module for 3-tonne electric forklift developed by HySA Systems and integrated by Hot Platinum (Pty) Ltd, South Africa. Main specifications of the power module are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Power module main specifications.

Donor vehicle	STILL RX60-30L
Bus voltage	80 VDC
Output power	~15 kW average, 30 kW peak
Dimensions	840 mm (W) x 1010 mm (D) x 777 mm (H)
Weight	1800...1900 kg
Stack	14.5 kW closed cathode PEMFC stack (Ballard);
H ₂ storage	Integrated MH storage unit, 20 Nm ³
Battery bank	Deep cycle lead-acid, 8...10 kWh

The BoP was designed around Ballard 9SSL/75 Cell FC stack, and its main components included: air supply, H₂

storage and supply, the closed circuit liquid stack cooling / MH heating, and power conditioning and control subsystems. The MH tank has dimensions of 704 mm (W) x 970 mm (D) x 270 mm (H), weight ~1200 kg and combines functions of H₂ storage and vehicle ballast thus adding flexibility to the layout of the BoP components within strict space constrains of the application. Direct integration of the MH tank in the power module allowed to decrease minimum H₂ pressure on the high-pressure side of H₂ subsystem from 13.5 to 3-4 bar and to use more stable MH resulting in a lower refuelling pressure (100-150 against 185 bar) at the similar useable H₂ storage capacity and refuelling time as compared to the commercial FC power module with MH extension tank [2].

Figure 1. Fuel cell powered module before its installation into the forklift compartment (left), tests under VDI2198/VDI60 protocol (right).

The power module provided stable operation of the forklift during 60 complete cycles of the VDI60 test carried out at ambient temperature of 27 °C. MH tank temperature during the test was as high as 50 °C indicating sufficient supply of heat released during the stack operation to the MH. Load energy consumption at 60 VDI cycles/hour was 9.564 kWh/h compared to 7.5 kWh/h claimed by forklift manufacturer that indicates more aggressive driving. BoP consumption during 60 VDI cycles was 5.138 kWh/h.

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References

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